

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

BASIC PRINCIPLES AND PATTERNS OF EVENT TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Event tourism is one of the most rapidly developing segments within the tourism industry. Events are considered a vital component of the tourism sector as they significantly influence the dynamic development of destinations, their competitiveness, and marketing strategies. This sector of the tourism industry is focused on organizing and attracting tourists to various events, mass gatherings, and occasions that occur in specific places and at specific times. This article discusses the basic principles and patterns, understanding and taking into account which helps organizers of event tourism to create unique and attractive events that contribute to the successful realization of the potential of the region and attract tourists from all over the world.

Keywords: event tourism, events, tourists, organization, fundamental principles, development patterns.

In the era of rapid development of high technologies and fast-paced lifestyles, people seek to escape the daily hustle and enrich their experiences with vibrant and memorable moments. One of the most appealing and intriguing ways to travel has become event tourism – a unique phenomenon that combines cultural immersion and participation in exciting events. This form of tourism allows each participant to witness and actively engage in vivid cultural, sports, art-related, and other events, which are planned in advance and possess temporary uniqueness.

Event tourism is an integral part of the broader tourism industry, directed towards visiting a destination at a specific time, tied to some event or happening in the life of a community or society [1, p. 37].

Event tourism is gaining popularity in our time, attracting those who seek to enrich their experiences and broaden their horizons. Mass gatherings, where people from all corners of the world converge to relish the vibrant atmosphere and unique impressions, have become particularly enticing for those in search of something extraordinary in their travels. Event tourism refers to a type of tourism in which travel is tied to specific events or occasions. The reasons for these tourist trips can encompass various events from the realms of sports, culture, business, social, and political life [2, p. 12].

However, event tourism is not just a source of pleasure and entertainment; it also plays a crucial role in the development of territories. It contributes to shaping the region's image, attracting investments, and enhancing cultural exchange and international cooperation. Each event becomes an opportunity for the local community to showcase its uniqueness and present its traditions, arts, and culture. Nowadays, several dozen cities worldwide specialize in the event economy [3, p. 38].

From massive festivals that annually attract thousands of experience seekers to unique cultural events that embody the spirit and heritage of nations, event tourism offers travelers an unparalleled opportunity to explore the world in all its manifestations. Immersing oneself in the local customs and traditions, engaging

with like-minded individuals from every corner of the planet, broadening horizons, and enriching one's spiritual world are just a few of the delights that await those who opt for event tourism. But what principles and patterns underlie this form of travel?

Event tourism represents a distinctive and dynamic form of travel encompassing a multitude of events that attract tourists from all around the globe. According to several authors, the organizational system of this type of tourism includes the following elements: the functions of event tourism, the areas that provide employment through the development of event tourism, and the key participants in the event tourism sector [4, p. 27].

The fundamental principles that shape this form of tourism determine its successful functioning and development, offering a rewarding experience for travelers and benefiting the local community.

The first key principle is the concept of events. Successful events are carefully planned with clearly defined objectives and tasks that take into account the interests and needs of the target audience. Event planning must be effective to ensure their attractiveness and uniqueness, contributing to attracting tourists and promoting events on a global level.

The second principle is related to cultural and identity significance. Event tourism is closely intertwined with the cultural heritage and traditions of the region where the events take place. Reflecting and preserving unique cultural features helps attract tourists interested in immersing themselves in the local culture and enriching their experiences.

Coordination and partnership represent the third principle in the formation of event tourism. Successful events require collaboration among various stakeholders, including organizers, governmental and local authorities, the business sector, educational institutions, and volunteer organizations. Close cooperation enables efficient event management and ensures its successful implementation.

The principle of sustainability and mutual benefit plays a crucial role in the development of event tourism. Event development should be based on sustainable

principles, considering ecological, socio-cultural, and economic aspects. Mutually beneficial conditions for tourists and the local community ensure long-term success and strengthen the region's position in the tourism industry.

The last but equally important principle is marketing and promotion. To attract tourists and promote event tourism, effective marketing strategies and promotion tools are necessary. Raising awareness among potential participants and positioning events at the global level contribute to successful tourist attraction and the promotion of the region's tourism potential.

Studying the fundamental principles of event tourism formation is a crucial step in understanding this

phenomenon and its impact on various societal spheres. Scientific analysis of these principles allows optimizing event organization, developing new appealing events, and fostering the development of regional tourism potential.

The regularities of event tourism formation are trends and characteristics that manifest during the development and organization of event-based activities. They define the fundamental principles and approaches to creating successful and attractive events for tourists. Here are some of the key regularities of event tourism formation (figure 1), (developed by the author):

Figure 1. Main Patterns of Event Tourism Formation.

- target audience. Each event must be planned with a specific target audience in mind. Understanding the needs and interests of tourists allows for the creation of an event that is attractive and meaningful to visitors.

- uniqueness and attractiveness. Events possessing unique characteristics and interesting features attract more tourists. Creating something special and one-of-a-kind helps capture attention and generate interest.

- collaboration and partnership. Successful event tourism requires collaboration among various stakeholders, including organizers, governmental and local authorities, the business sector, educational institutions, and volunteer organizations.

- planning and coordination. Effective planning and coordination are key aspects of successful event tourism. Developing a clear plan, considering the main stages of organization, and efficiently allocating resources contribute to successful event implementation.

- embracing innovation. Event tourism is constantly evolving, and it is important to embrace new ideas and innovative approaches. Utilizing new technologies, creative concepts, and current trends enables the creation of events that cater to modern tourists' needs.

- sustainability and responsibility. Event organization should be based on principles of sustainable development, considering ecological, socio-cultural, and economic aspects. Maintaining a balance between tourists' needs and preserving natural and cultural resources is a key factor for long-term success.

- marketing and promotion. Effective marketing strategies and promotion tools play a crucial role in attracting tourists and promoting event tourism both at the international and local levels.

Understanding and incorporating these regularities assists event tourism organizers in creating unique and appealing events, contributing to the successful realization of a region's potential and attracting tourists from around the world.

Researching the principles and patterns of event tourism is an integral and crucial aspect for optimizing event organization and maximizing the tourism potential of regions. The development of event tourism not only contributes to the successful realization of a region's potential and attracts tourists from around the world but also fosters diverse and sustainable growth in the tourism industry as a whole.

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ON OPTIMIZATION OF ELECTRICITY TARIFFS

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ОБ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ТАРИФОВ НА ЭЛЕКТРОЭНЕРГИЮ

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Abstract

The paper considers the economic and mathematical model of tariff optimization. We study the problem of finding the Ramsey price using the function of the general standard of living. The paper also considers generalizations of the tariff optimization model. The problem of determining prices in the electric power industry, especially tariffs for electricity for the population, is one of the most important and discussed problems. Tariff policy as an instrument of industry management is designed to promote economic efficiency and the realization of public interests.

Аннотация

В работе рассмотрена экономико-математическая модель тарифной оптимизации. Исследуется задача нахождения цены Рамсея с помощью функции общего уровня жизни.

В работе также рассматриваются обобщения модели тарифной оптимизации. Проблема определения цен в электроэнергетике, особенно тарифов на электроэнергию для населения, является одной из наиболее важных и обсуждаемых проблем. Тарифная политика как инструмент управления промышленностью призвана способствовать достижению экономической эффективности и реализации общественных интересов.

Keywords: tariff, electricity, economic and mathematical model, regulation, optimization.

Ключевые слова: тариф, электроэнергия, экономико-математическая модель, регулирование, оптимизация.

1. Введение

В работе исследуется задача нахождения цены Рамсея, которая изучается в [1]. В отличие от этих работ, в работе учитывается условие неотрицательности цены и подробно исследуется модель тарифной оптимизации. Исследованы также частные случаи рассматриваемой модели. В работе также рассматриваются обобщения модели тарифной оптимизации, которая изучается в [2].

Каждому варианту реформирования электроэнергетики соответствуют свои механизмы ценообразования, адекватные структуре рынка. В мировой практике имеется значительный опыт применения различных моделей и методов формирования цен в электроэнергетике, как при вертикальной дезинтеграции, так и при сохранении вертикально интегрированных энергокомпаний.

Зарубежная литература, посвященная теории естественных монополий (ЕМ), предлагает широкий спектр моделей ценового регулирования, нацеленных на обеспечение оптимального уровня и структуры цен. Эти модели предполагают выделение естественно-монопольного ядра отрасли, исследование его устойчивости, выбор критерия оптимизации.

Действующие в настоящий момент принципы ценообразования в сфере ЕМ ориентированы лишь на установление тарифов, гарантирующих инвестиционную привлекательность соответствующих секторов за счет включения в тариф норм возврата капитала с учетом его доходности. Вопросы устойчивости ЕМ, а также оптимизации с точки зрения общественного благосостояния даже не ставятся. Между тем, регулирование цен, основанное на оптимизационных моделях ценообразования, могло бы обеспечить баланс интересов потребителей (доступные цены), регулируемых предприятий (финансовые результаты, привле-